

Macroeconomic Determinants of Nifty 50 Returns: Evidence from the ARDL Model

Ms. Riddhi R. Bhatwara
Research Scholar,
rbhatwara@gmail.com
Dr. Vinitkumar J. Varma
Assistant Professor,
Department of Commerce & Management,
BKNMU, Junagadh
vinvarma23@gamil.com

Abstract

This study investigates the effect of Foreign Portfolio Investment (FPI), the India VIX index, and the USD/INR exchange rate on Nifty 50 returns, using monthly data from January 2015 to December 2024. The ARDL Bounds Testing method was applied to examine the short-term and long-term associations between these variables. The Augmented Dickey-Fuller test confirmed that the variables were integrated at orders $I(0)$ and $I(1)$, thereby justifying the use of the ARDL model. The ARDL bounds test outcomes confirmed the presence of a long relationship between the variables. Long-term estimates indicate that FPI has a positive and significant effect on Nifty 50 returns. In contrast, the India VIX and the USD/INR exchange rate do not exert a significant long-term effect. However, the Error Correction Model (ECM) reveals that the India VIX and the USD/INR exchange rate negatively influence stock returns in the short period. Diagnostic and stability tests confirmed the reliability and stability of the estimated model. These results suggest valuable insights for investors, portfolio managers, and policymakers seeking to better understand the factors affecting the Indian stock market.

Keywords: *Nifty 50 Returns, Foreign Portfolio Investment, India VIX, USD/INR Exchange Rate, ARDL Model*

1. Introduction

The stock market of India has experienced rapid progress over the past decade, establishing itself as a major capital market among emerging economies. Economic growth, reforms in the financial sector, digital trading platforms, and improved financial literacy have encouraged more individual and institutional investors to invest in the stock market (NSE, 2025). The National Stock Exchange (NSE) has played an essential role in this evolution by providing a transparent and efficient trading platform. Based on the NSE's integrated annual report for the 2024–2025 fiscal year, the exchange hosted 2,720 listed companies and facilitated total capital

mobilization amounting to ₹18.7 trillion (18.7 lakh crore) during this period, with ₹4.3 trillion derived from equity issues (NSE, 2025). These developments underscore the stock market's growing importance in supporting economic growth. Concurrently, the Indian market has become progressively integrated with global financial markets. Consequently, stock market returns are affected not only by domestic monetary situations but also by foreign investment, investor sentiment, and the global economic climate (IMF, 2024). Thus, identifying the factors that impact stock returns has become a key area of research for investors, policymakers, portfolio managers, and researchers.

The Nifty 50 is the benchmark index of the National Stock Exchange of India (NSE); it comprises fifty huge corporations from numerous sectors of the Indian economy (NSE, 2025). It is broadly used to measure the performance of the stock market of India, as it encompasses leading companies characterized by high market capitalization and high liquidity. Investors, mutual funds, exchange-traded funds (ETFs), and financial institutions frequently use the Nifty 50 as a benchmark for investment decisions and portfolio evaluation. Consequently, studying the factors influencing Nifty 50 returns provides an understanding of the behavior and performance of the stock exchange (NSE, 2025).

Among the numerous factors influencing stock market returns, Foreign Portfolio Investment (FPI), the India VIX index, and the USD/INR exchange rate are considered particularly significant. Foreign portfolio investors boost market liquidity and facilitate price discovery through their investment activities (Hussain & Goswami, 2022). Still, their investment decisions are heavily influenced by global economic situations, rates of interest, geopolitical measures, and shifts in investor risk perception (Hussain & Goswami, 2022; International Monetary Fund [IMF], 2024). Consequently, fluctuations in FPI inflows and outflows often affect stock prices and market returns. Another key factor is the India VIX index, commonly known as the "fear index." It measures investor expectations regarding future market volatility (Vaswani & Padmaja, 2024). A rise in the India VIX signals increased market uncertainty and often prompts investors to exercise greater caution. The USD/INR exchange rate also plays a major role, as variations in the price of the Indian rupee impact corporate earnings, foreign investment choices, and the returns realized by international investors (Siddiqui & Roy, 2021; IMF, 2024). Given the close interdependence of these three variables, analyzing their combined impact provides a better comprehension of stock market behavior than studying each factor in isolation (Hussain & Goswami, 2022; Vaswani & Padmaja, 2024).

The period from 2015 to 2024 is particularly well-suited for this study, as the Indian monetary market experienced several significant economic and financial events during these years. Notable examples include demonetization, the application of the Goods and Services Tax (GST), the COVID-19 pandemic, the post-pandemic economic recovery, shifts in global monetary policies, and geopolitical tensions (IMF, 2024). These events led to significant changes in foreign investment flows, market volatility, exchange rates, and securities market performance. Consequently, this period offers a favorable framework for examining the impact of

these factors on the Nifty 50 index returns. Many earlier studies have examined the relationship between stock market returns and individual variables such as foreign investment, exchange charges, inflation, interest rates, or market volatility (Hussain & Goswami, 2022; Siddiqui & Roy, 2021; Vaswani & Padmaja, 2024). Though, comparatively limited studies have observed the combined effect of Foreign Portfolio Investment (FPI) flows, the India VIX index, and the USD/INR exchange rate on Nifty 50 returns using recent monthly data. Additionally, several previous studies depend on conventional econometric methods that fail to clearly distinguish between short-term and long-term relationships (Pesaran et al., 2001). There is, therefore, a need to adopt a more suitable econometric approach capable of analyzing both the immediate and long-term effects of these variables on stock market earnings.

The study employs the ARDL (Autoregressive Distributed Lag) bounds testing approach to address this research gap. The ARDL model is suitable because it allows for the estimation of both short and long period relations between variables, even when they are integrated at different levels, such as I(0) and I(1) (Pesaran et al., 2001). This study examines the impact of foreign portfolio investments, the India VIX index, and the USD/INR exchange rate on Nifty 50 returns, using monthly data from 2015 to 2024. The main purpose of the study is to enrich the existing literature by shedding new light on the factors affecting returns of the stock market in India. The findings could also assist investors, portfolio managers, financial institutions, and policymakers in better understanding how foreign capital flows, market uncertainty, and exchange rate fluctuations affect the Indian stock market.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Foreign Portfolio Investment and Stock Market Returns

Foreign portfolio investment (FPI) constitutes a major source of funds for emerging stock markets, particularly India's. It enhances market liquidity, fosters price formation, and stimulates trading activity. However, FPI flows are heavily influenced by worldwide economic situations, monetary policy, exchange rate fluctuations, and investor sentiment. Consequently, variations in foreign investment can significantly impact stock market returns. Numerous current studies have observed the relationship between FPI and stock market performance. Parab and Reddy (2020) highlighted a noteworthy association between foreign institutional investment and stock market returns in India, although this relationship evolved following demonetization. Siddiqui and Roy (2021) revealed that exchange rate variations influence foreign investment decisions, which in turn affect stock market performance. Hussain and Goswami (2022) demonstrated that industrial production, market capitalization, exchange rates, and foreign direct investment (FDI) are important determinants of FPI flows in both the short and long term. Similarly, Kumari et al. (2023) established that stock market functioning, exchange rates, inflation, and interest rates significantly influence foreign institutional investment in India. Furthermore, Yadav and Kumar (2023) noted that the association between FPI and stock market returns

strengthened during the COVID period due to heightened market uncertainty. Earlier studies advise that FPI act an essential role in stock market performance.

2.2. India VIX and Returns of the Stock Market

The India VIX is commonly used to assess market uncertainty and investor sentiment in the securities market of India. It reflects the expected instability of the Nifty 50 index, calculated based on option prices. A high India VIX value indicates heightened uncertainty and greater risk expectations among investors, whereas a lower value suggests relatively stable market conditions. The India VIX is considered a significant indicator for understanding variations in market returns. Various studies have surveyed the connection between the India VIX and stock market performance. Dhanaiah et al. (2013) highlighted a significant negative relationship between the India VIX and Nifty returns, indicating that increased market uncertainty is generally linked with lower stock market returns. Similarly, Shaikh and Padhi (2014) noted that the India VIX reacts more strongly to market declines than to gains. More recently, Vaswani and Padmaja (2024) found that market unpredictability and investor sentiment have significant long-term impacts on returns. These outcomes recommend that the India VIX helps as a key indicator of market behavior and asset decisions. Previous studies demonstrate that the India VIX plays a fundamental role in explaining stock market movements.

2.3. USD/INR Exchange Rate and Stock Market Returns

The rate of exchange is a major macroeconomic factor influencing market performance, mostly in emerging economies such as India. Changeability in the USD/INR exchange rate affect export competitiveness, corporate profitability, foreign investment decisions, and the returns realized by international investors. Consequently, exchange rate differences can affect stock prices and overall market performance. Some research has studied this relationship. Siddiqui and Roy (2021) highlighted that exchange rate variations significantly influence foreign investment decisions and stock market implementation in India. Vaswani and Padmaja (2024) also revealed that exchange rate fluctuations, like other macroeconomic factors, have a significant long-term effect on stock market returns. Similarly, Bhattacharjee (2024) observed that positive and negative exchange rate movements affect the Indian stock market differently, thereby underscoring the asymmetric nature of this relationship. Previous studies confirm the existence of a strong connection between fluctuations in the rate of exchange and stock market performance.

2.4. Research Gap

Many earlier studies have examined the effect of foreign portfolio investment (FPI), the India VIX index, and the USD/INR exchange rate on stock market performance. However, most of this study has evaluated these factors in isolation or focused on specific economic events. Consequently, there is a partial suggestion about how these three variables jointly influence Nifty 50 returns. Moreover, rare studies have employed the

Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) approach to explore the short- and long-term associations between these variables. This study, therefore, aims to fill this gap by analyzing the combined impact of FPI, the India VIX index, and the USD/INR exchange rate on Nifty 50 returns, with the help of monthly data from January 2015 to December 2024 and the ARDL bounds testing method.

3. Objective of the study

To investigate the influence of Foreign Portfolio Investment (FPI), the India VIX index, and the USD/INR exchange rate on Nifty 50 returns by analyzing short- and long-term relationships using the ARDL bounds testing approach.

4. Hypothesis of the study

Based on the study purpose and the existing literature, the following hypotheses are proposed

H1: Foreign Portfolio Investment (FPI), India VIX, and the USD/INR exchange rate have an important influence on Nifty 50 returns.

H2: A significant long-run relationship exists among Foreign Portfolio Investment (FPI), India VIX, the USD/INR exchange rate, and Nifty 50 returns.

5. Research Methodology

5.1. Research Design

This research employs a quantitative research methodology to study the influence of foreign portfolio investment (FPI), the India VIX index, and the USD/INR exchange rate on Nifty 50 returns. A quantitative approach is appropriate, as it enables the analysis of numerical data using econometric techniques to identify short-term and long-term relationships among the selected variables.

5.2. Sources of the Data

This study depends on secondary data from reliable public sources. Monthly closing values for the Nifty 50 index and the India VIX were collected from the National Stock Exchange (NSE). Monthly net Foreign Portfolio Investment (FPI) flows into equities were gathered from the National Securities Depository Limited (NSDL), while the monthly USD/INR exchange rate was obtained from the RBI (Reserve Bank of India).

5.3. Time-Period

The study includes the period from January 2015 to December 2024, comprising 120 monthly observations. This period encompasses several major economic and financial events, such as demonetization, the application of the Goods and Services Tax (GST), the COVID-19 pandemic, the post-pandemic economic recovery, and shifts in global monetary policies. These events make this period a relevant analytical framework for examining the relationships between the selected variables.

5.4. Need for the Study

The securities market of India has become progressively interconnected with global financial markets, making stock returns further complex due to both domestic and international developments. Among the various factors influencing market performance, Foreign Portfolio Investment (FPI), the India VIX index, and the USD/INR exchange rate are of particular importance, as they affect capital flows, investor sentiment, market uncertainty, and investment decisions. These factors are closely interdependent: exchange rate fluctuations can impact foreign investment decisions, while changes in market uncertainty affect both investor behavior and foreign capital flows, ultimately impacting stock returns. While earlier studies have observed these variables individually, few have analyzed their combined impact on Nifty 50 index returns using recent data. Consequently, this study aims to deepen the understanding of how these three macro-financial variables jointly influence the Indian stock market, applying the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) approach.

5.5. Model specification

To study the association between the selected variables, the following regression model is specified:

- General Regression Model

$$RETURN_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 FPI_t + \beta_2 VIX_t + \beta_3 USD_t + \varepsilon_t$$

Since the variables are integrated in different orders, the bounds testing approach ARDL (autoregressive model with lagged lags), developed by Pesaran et al. (2001), is applied to estimate short-term and long-term connections among variables. Data analysis was carried out using EViews software. The study used the following statistical and econometric techniques:

- ARDL Model

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta RETURN_t = & \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha_i \Delta RETURN_{t-i} + \sum_{j=0}^{q_1} \beta_j \Delta FPI_{t-j} + \sum_{k=0}^{q_2} \gamma_k \Delta VIX_{t-k} + \sum_{l=0}^{q_3} \delta_l \Delta USD_{t-l} \\ & + \lambda_1 RETURN_{t-1} + \lambda_2 FPI_{t-1} + \lambda_3 VIX_{t-1} + \lambda_4 USD_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \end{aligned}$$

- Long-Run Model

$$RETURN_t = \theta_0 + \theta_1 FPI_t + \theta_2 VIX_t + \theta_3 USD_t + \mu_t$$

- Error Correction Model (ECM)

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta RETURN_t = & \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha_i \Delta RETURN_{t-i} + \sum_{j=0}^{q_1} \beta_j \Delta FPI_{t-j} + \sum_{k=0}^{q_2} \gamma_k \Delta VIX_{t-k} + \sum_{l=0}^{q_3} \delta_l \Delta USD_{t-l} \\ & + \psi ECT_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \end{aligned}$$

6. Results and Discussion

6.1. Descriptive statistics

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics Results

Variable	Nifty 50 Returns	FPI	India VIX	USD/INR
Mean	0.9821	4881.98	16.6846	75.1839
Median	1.1347	2836.00	15.5725	73.9936
Maximum	13.697	93538.00	64.4075	89.9198
Minimum	-26.456	-118203.0	9.67750	63.6878
Std. Dev.	4.7626	31578.30	6.36094	7.47834
Skewness	-1.4047	-0.444068	3.99780	0.21293
Kurtosis	11.007	5.250515	28.2875	1.7839
Jarque-Bera	357.03	29.02412	3487.63	8.2318
Probability	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000

Sources: Author's computation using EViews Software

Table 1 presents the descriptive analysis for the study variables. Nifty 50 returns showed a positive monthly average over the study period, although the wide gap between maximum and minimum values indicates significant market fluctuations. Among all the variables, Foreign Portfolio Investment (FPI) exhibited the highest variability, reflecting frequent fluctuations in foreign investment flows. The India VIX index also experienced notable variations, signaling periods of heightened market uncertainty, whereas the USD/INR exchange rate remained relatively more stable. The Jarque-Bera test outcomes are significant for all variables, advising that the data do not have a normal distribution, a common characteristic of financial time series.

6.2. Correlation Analysis

Table 2. Correlation Matrix

Variable	Nifty 50 Returns	FPI	India VIX	USD/INR
Nifty 50 Returns	1.0000			
FPI	0.5855	1.0000		
India VIX	-0.3512	-0.3442	1.0000	
USD/INR	-0.0381	-0.0381	-0.0755	1.0000

Sources: Author's computation using EViews Software

Table 2 presents the matrix of correlation for the research variables. The results reveal a moderate positive association between Nifty 50 returns and foreign portfolio investment (FPI), indicating that higher levels of foreign investment are usually linked with higher stock market returns. The India VIX index shows a moderate

negative relationship with Nifty 50 returns, suggesting that increased market uncertainty is accompanied by lower returns. The USD/INR exchange rate displays a weak negative relationship with stock market returns. Furthermore, all correlation coefficients are below the 0.80 threshold, indicating that multicollinearity is not an issue in this study. Consequently, the independent variables can be included in the ARDL model.

6.3. Augmented Dickey–Fuller (ADF) Unit Root Test

Table 3. ADF Unit Root Test Results

Variable	Level ADF Statistic	First Difference I(1)	Order of Integration	P-Value	Decision
Nifty 50 Returns	-11.4091	-	I(0)	0.0000	Stationary
FPI	-4.9763	-	I(0)	0.0001	Stationary
India VIX	-5.2439	-	I(0)	0.0000	Stationary
USD/INR	0.2922	-11.4304	I(1)	0.9770	Stationary after first difference

Sources: Author’s computation using EViews Software

The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root test was conducted to observe the stationarity of the research variables before estimating the ARDL model. Table 3 presents the ADF test results. These results indicate that Nifty 50 returns, foreign portfolio investment (FPI), and the India VIX index are stationary at level I(0), whereas the USD/INR exchange rate becomes stationary after first-differencing I(1). Given that the variables are integrated at levels I(0) and I(1) and none are integrated at level I(2), the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) approach is appropriate for examining the short and long-period relationships between these variables.

6.4. ARDL Bounds Test for Cointegration

Table 4. ARDL Bounds Test for Cointegration

Test Statistic	Value	
F-statistic	16.2718	
Number of Regressors (K)	3	
Sample Size	111	
Decision	Cointegration Exists	
Critical Values (Asymptotic, n=1000)		
Significant Level	I(0)	I(1)
10%	2.37	3.2
5%	2.79	3.67
2.5%	3.15	4.08
1%	3.65	4.66

Sources: Author's computation using EViews Software

The ARDL bounds test was conducted to examine the presence of a long-run connection between the variables under study. Table 4 presents the test results. The calculated F-statistic (16.27) exceeds the upper bound critical value at the 1% significance level. Consequently, the null hypothesis of no long-run relationship is rejected, confirming the presence of cointegration among Nifty 50 index returns, foreign portfolio investment (FPI), the India VIX index, and the USD/INR exchange rate. This result indicates that the variables move together in the long run, despite short-term fluctuations. Therefore, it is appropriate to estimate the long-run coefficients and the error correction model (ECM).

6.5. Long-Run Coefficient Estimation

Table 5. Long-Run coefficient Estimation Results

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	P-value	Decision
FPI	0.0000	0.0000	3.6654	0.0004	Significant
India VLX	0.0242	0.0441	0.5492	0.5841	Not Significant
USD/INR	-0.0075	0.0273	-0.2742	0.7845	Not Significant
Constant	1.0388	2.2711	0.4573	0.6484	Not Significant

Sources: Author's computation using EViews Software

Table 5 presents the long-term coefficients estimated using the ARDL model. The results show that foreign portfolio investment (FPI) has a positive and significant effect on Nifty 50 returns ($\beta = 4.85E-05$, $p < 0.01$), representing that increased foreign investment provides to higher stock returns in the long run. In contrast, Indian VIX and USD/INR exchange rates have statistically insignificant coefficients, suggesting that their long-term effects on Nifty 50 returns are not significant during the study period. Overall, the results indicate that FPI is the only significant long-term determinant of Nifty 50 returns among the variables considered in this research.

6.6. ECM-(Error Correction Model)

Table 6. ECM Results

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	P-value	Decision
ECT (-1)	-1.2820	0.1519	-8.4369	0.0000	Significant
D(FPI)	0.0000	0.0000	6.5519	0.0000	Significant
D(FPI (-1))	0.0000	0.0000	0.8653	0.3890	Not Significant
D(FPI (-2))	0.0000	0.0000	1.2533	0.2131	Not Significant
D(FPI (-3))	-0.0000	0.0000	-1.6702	0.0981	Not Significant
D (India VIX)	-0.3781	0.0572	-6.6101	0.0000	Significant
D (India VIX (-1))	-0.0364	0.0757	-0.4812	0.6314	Not Significant
D (India VIX (-2))	-0.1533	0.0716	-2.1404	0.0348	Significant
D (India VIX (-3))	-0.1285	0.0580	-2.2155	0.0291	Significant
D (USD/INR)	-0.9120	0.2954	-3.0875	0.0026	Significant

Sources: Author's computation using EViews Software

Table 6 presents the short-term results of the error correction model (ECM). ECT is negative and significant ($\beta = -1.2821$, $p < 0.01$), confirming the existence of a stable long-term equilibrium between the study variables. The coefficient indicates that short-term deviations from the long-term equilibrium are corrected relatively quickly. In the short term, changes in foreign portfolio investment (FPI) have a positive and significant effect on Nifty 50 index returns, whereas changes in the India VIX and the USD/INR exchange rate exert a negative effect. These outcomes revealed that foreign investment supports stock market performance, while increased market uncertainty and exchange rate fluctuations reduce short-term stock market returns.

6.7. Diagnostic Tests

Table 7. Diagnostic Tests Results

Diagnostic Test	p-value	Decision
Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test	0.4496	No Serial Correlation
Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Heteroskedasticity Test	0.8860	No Heteroskedasticity
Jarque-Bera Normality Test	0.7671	Residuals are Normally Distributed

Sources: Author's computation using EViews Software

Diagnostic tests were conducted to examine the reliability of the estimated ARDL model. The Breusch-Godfrey LM test for autocorrelation shows that the model is free from autocorrelation, with a p-value greater than 0.05. Similarly, the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test confirms the absence of heteroskedasticity, suggesting that the residual variance is constant. Furthermore, the Jarque-Bera normality test shows that the residuals

follow a normal distribution. These findings support that the estimated ARDL model satisfies the required diagnostic assumptions and yields reliable estimates.

6.8. Stability Tests

The stability of the estimated ARDL model was examined using the CUSUM and CUSUM of Squares (CUSUMSQ) tests. Figures 1 and 2 present the test results.

Figure 1. CUSUM Test

Sources: Author’s computation using EViews Software

The CUSUM curve remains within the 5% critical limits throughout the study period, indicating that the probable coefficients are constant over time. Similarly, the CUSUMSQ curve also stays within the 5% critical limits, although it approaches the upper limit towards the end of the sample period. As neither curve crosses the critical limits, the results confirm that the estimated ARDL model is structurally stable and suitable for analyzing the connection amongst foreign portfolio investment (FPI), the India VIX index, the USD/INR exchange rate, and Nifty 50 returns.

Figure 2. CUSUM of Squares (CUSUMSQ) Test

Sources: Author's computation using EViews Software

7. Conclusion

This study analyzed the influence of foreign portfolio investment (FPI), the India VIX index, and the USD/INR exchange rate on Nifty 50 returns, with monthly data from 2015 to 2024. The ARDL bounds test confirmed the existence of a long-term relationship between these variables. Long-term findings indicated that FPI has a positive and statistically strong impact on Nifty 50 returns, whereas the India VIX index and the USD/INR rate of exchange have no significant long-term effect. However, the error correction model (ECM) revealed that, in the short term, FPI positively influences stock returns, while the India VIX index and the USD/INR rate have adverse effects.

Stability and Diagnostic tests have proven that the estimated ARDL model is statistically reliable, free from major econometric issues, and stable throughout the study period. Overall, the results advise that foreign portfolio investment is an important driver of stock market performance, whereas market uncertainty and exchange rate fluctuations primarily affect short-term returns. This study suggests notable insights for investors, portfolio managers, financial institutions, and policymakers by enhancing the understanding of how external financial factors influence the Indian stock market. These findings can guide investment decisions, portfolio management strategies, and policies aimed at maintaining market stability.

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